

Come to the dark side! The role of functional traits in shaping dark diversity patterns of Southeast European hoverflies

Journal:	<i>Ecological Entomology</i>
Manuscript ID	19-0078-EEN.R2
Manuscript Type:	Original Article
Date Submitted by the Author:	n/a
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Keywords:	disturbance, functional characteristics, insects, missing species, richness, Syrphidae, vegetation types

Come to the dark side! The role of functional traits in shaping dark diversity patterns of Southeast European hoverflies

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- This study determines the levels of hoverfly dark diversity across different vegetation types in Southeast Europe and detects functional traits contributing to species being a part of dark diversity.
- The highest dark diversity was found for Southwest Balkan sub-Mediterranean mixed oak forest type, whereas the lowest was in Mediterranean mixed forest type.
- Three larval feeding modes (saproxylic, and phytophagous of bulbs or roots) were found to be most important for determining the probability of a species contributing to hoverfly dark diversity.

1 **Come to the dark side! The role of functional traits in shaping**
2 **dark diversity patterns of Southeast European hoverflies**

3

4 Short title: Hoverfly dark diversity in SE Europe

5

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21

22 **Abstract**

- 23 1. Dark diversity represents the set of species that can
24 potentially inhabit a given area under particular ecological
25 conditions, but are currently 'missing' from a site. This
26 concept allows characterization of the mechanisms
27 determining why species are sometimes absent from an
28 area that seems ecologically suitable for them.
- 29 2. Our aim was to determine the dark diversity of hoverflies in
30 Southeast Europe and to discuss the role of different
31 functional traits that might increase the likelihood of
32 species contributing to dark diversity. Based on expert
33 opinion, the Syrph the Net database and known occurrences
34 of species, we estimated species pools, observed and dark
35 diversities within each of 11 defined vegetation types for
36 564 hoverfly species registered in SE Europe. To detect the
37 most important functional traits contributing to species
38 being in dark diversity across different vegetation types, we
39 used a random forest algorithm and respective statistics for
40 variable importance.
- 41 3. The highest dark diversity was found for Southwest Balkan
42 sub-Mediterranean mixed oak forest type, whereas the
43 lowest was in Mediterranean mixed forest type. Three
44 larval feeding modes (saproxylic, and phytophagous of
45 bulbs or roots) were found to be most important for

46 determining the probability of a species contributing to
47 hoverfly dark diversity, based on univariate correlations
48 and random forest analysis.

49 4. This study shows that studying dark diversity might
50 provide important insights into what drives community
51 assembly in SE European hoverflies, especially its missing
52 components and contributes to more precise conservation
53 prioritization of both hoverfly species and their habitats.

54

55 **KEYWORDS:** disturbance; functional characteristics; insects;
56 missing species; richness; Syrphidae; vegetation types

57

58 **Introduction**

59 To understand and protect biodiversity, detailed information on
60 different aspects of biodiversity, such as local species richness or
61 the presence of specialist species, is essential (Hooper *et al.*, 2012;
62 Barton & Evans, 2017). However, knowledge on extant
63 biodiversity alone may not allow interesting patterns related to
64 missing components of communities to be uncovered (Pärtel *et al.*,
65 2011). Recent findings (Pärtel *et al.*, 2011, Partel, 2014; Ronk *et*
66 *al.*, 2015; Lewis *et al.*, 2017) have shown that so-called ‘dark
67 diversity’ could reveal new biodiversity patterns that would not be
68 evident from investigating only observed diversity. The species

69 that are not recorded at a particular site, but that belong to its
70 species pool and could potentially co-occur in the site, given its
71 biotic, abiotic and dispersal limitations, constitute the dark
72 diversity of that site (Pärtel *et al.*, 2011). In order to examine dark
73 diversity of a target site, the habitat-specific species pool must be
74 established, i.e. the set of species that are available and can inhabit
75 a given area under designated ecological conditions (Cornell &
76 Harrison 2014; Zobel, 2016).

77 Figure 1. Schematic diagram illustrating species pool, observed
78 and dark diversity.

79
80 Hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) play important roles in providing
81 vital ecosystem services such as pollination (Ssymank & Kearns,
82 2009; Petanidou *et al.*, 2011; Jauker *et al.*, 2012), waste
83 decomposition (Gilbert, 1985) and biological control (White *et al.*,
84 1995; Blaauw & Isaacs, 2012; Day *et al.*, 2015). Recent studies
85 have shown that hoverflies can serve as valuable model organisms
86 in studies of climate change (Kaloveloni *et al.*, 2015; Radenković
87 *et al.*, 2017; Miličić *et al.*, 2018), urbanization (Bates *et al.*, 2011;
88 Verboven *et al.*, 2014), landscape structure (Power *et al.*, 2016) or
89 land use (Aguirre-Gutiérrez *et al.*, 2015; Földesi & Kovács-
90 Hostyánszki, 2016; Lucas *et al.*, 2017).

91 Southeast Europe (SE Europe) is one of the richest areas globally
92 in terms of hoverfly diversity, mostly due to its complex geology
93 (Cvetković *et al.*, 2016) and climatic diversity (Vukelić *et al.*,
94 2018). Pronounced human-induced environmental changes have
95 taken place in this region and left their mark on its vegetation
96 (Marinova *et al.*, 2012). SE Europe, as an environmentally
97 heterogeneous and dynamic region, is particularly suitable for
98 examining hoverfly dark diversity. Because of the close connection
99 of hoverflies to their habitats (Speight & Castella, 2016), species
100 ranges continuously change together with the changing
101 environment.

102 Ecological studies of hoverflies increasingly use functional traits
103 (i.e. physiological, phenological, morphological or behavioral
104 characteristics), rather than simply focusing on their taxonomic
105 identity (Sommagio & Burgio 2014; Jauker *et al.*, 2019). Various
106 authors have examined the response of hoverfly functional
107 diversity to different environmental aspects including land use and
108 land management (Schweiger *et al.*, 2007; de Groot *et al.*, 2016;
109 Winsa *et al.*, 2017), climate change (Aguirre-Gutiérrez *et al.*,
110 2016) or habitat heterogeneity (Larrieu *et al.*, 2015). However,
111 specific functional traits promoting higher levels of dark diversity,
112 and absence from apparently suitable sites, have yet to be
113 determined.

114 This study tests for the first time the hypothesis that functional
115 traits affect dark diversity of hoverflies, revealing ecological
116 patterns reflected in hoverfly communities. Based on known
117 occurrence records of hoverflies in SE Europe, the Syrph the Net
118 (StN) database (Speight *et al.*, 2015), and expert opinion, we aim
119 to assess the dark diversity of hoverflies in this region, as well as
120 discuss the role of different functional traits in explaining the
121 patterns of dark diversity.

122

123 **Methods**

124 **Study area and species occurrences**

125 The study area covers the Balkan Peninsula and the Aegean islands
126 governed by Greece. Information on all species registered in this
127 area, as well as their distribution, was extracted from the database
128 of the Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
129 (FSUNS). This database is a result of the hoverfly monitoring
130 program across SE Europe from 1950 to 2017, during which the
131 sampling of hoverflies was conducted using a consistent census
132 protocol (see Radenković *et al.*, 2017 for more details).
133 Additionally, we included data from published **materials** referring
134 to this territory, as well as data obtained from different museum
135 and private collections. Only specimens for which precise
136 distributional data were available were used in our analyses. Exact

137 locality coordinates were checked for accuracy where provided.
138 Records for which only locality names were available were
139 assigned coordinates using Google Earth (Google Inc., 2018). In
140 total, we considered 63814 occurrence records of 564 species.

141

142 **Vegetation types**

143 To assess the distribution of hoverflies within different vegetation
144 types represented in SE Europe, we used the map of natural
145 vegetation of Europe (Bohn *et al.*, 2000). The map was modified
146 by merging similar vegetation types (e.g. multiple types describing
147 beech forests) to generate a total of 11 categories (Fig. 2), which
148 correspond better with known biological and ecological
149 characteristics of hoverfly species.

150

151 Figure 2. Vegetation types in Southeast Europe.

152

153 **Functional traits**

154 Data on functional traits of hoverflies were collected from multiple
155 sources. We used published data (Speight *et al.*, 2015; Speight,
156 2017), expert opinion-based data, and fieldwork experience
157 spanning 35 years regarding biological and ecological
158 characteristics of species. Information on wing and body length of
159 analyzed species was not available in the literature, but because we

160 considered these traits to be biologically significant, we measured
161 it using a Nikon SMZ 745T stereomicroscope. Wing length was
162 measured from the insertion point on the thorax to the tip of the
163 wing, while body length was measured as the length from the tip of
164 the frontal prominence (excluding antenna) to the tip of the
165 abdomen. We measured four specimens of each species (two male
166 and two female), and used the averaged value as a variable in
167 further analyses. Information on body shape and body pile of
168 registered species was obtained based on visual inspection of the
169 insects. All measurements and inspection of specimens were
170 conducted in the Laboratory for Biodiversity Research and
171 Conservation, in the Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty
172 of Sciences, University of Novi Sad. Information on larval feeding
173 mode, duration of larval development, number of generations,
174 inundation tolerance, distribution, period of flight and number of
175 habitats were obtained from the literature, while height at which
176 species fly, flight ability and human impact tolerance were expert
177 opinion-based. Functional traits with multiple non-mutually-
178 exclusive trait states were coded as dummy variables. Additionally,
179 if possible and where justified, categorical traits were transformed
180 into ordinal variables. In small number of cases, if the trait state for
181 the given species was unknown, the species was assigned the most

182 common trait state found in other members of that genus. The list
183 of functional traits used in the analyses is presented in Tab. 1.

184

185 Table 1. Functional traits and trait states of hoverflies in SE
186 Europe.

187

188 **Estimation of dark diversity**

189 Species pools for each defined vegetation type separately were
190 compiled based on expert opinion and information from the StN
191 database. The database compiles information about distribution
192 and habitat preferences for European hoverfly species and has been
193 successfully used for habitat evaluations (Speight & Castella,
194 2001; Sommaggio & Burgio, 2014; Popov *et al.*, 2017).

195 Each species was assigned to any
196 major vegetation type in SE Europe defined in this study in which
197 it can occur, taking into consideration its known distribution across
198 Europe, as well as the known biological and ecological preferences
199 of that species (Speight *et al.*, 2015; Speight, 2017).

200 All estimations and analyses were made using the full dataset
201 (across vegetation types). To quantify observed diversity,
202 occurrence records were plotted on the vegetation map using open
203 source GIS software (QGIS Development Team, 2009). Dark
204 diversity was calculated for each vegetation type separately as the

205 difference between the species pool and the observed species
206 belonging to that particular pool (i.e. the number of potential
207 species missing from each vegetation type). Percentage of dark
208 diversity across all vegetation types was calculated as the ratio
209 between dark diversity and the sum of dark and observed diversity.
210 To establish how much of the habitat-specific species pool is
211 actually realized (Pärtel *et al.* 2013; Ronk *et al.* 2015) in each
212 vegetation type, we calculated Diversity Completeness as the log
213 ratio between observed species richness and dark diversity (Ronk,
214 2016).

215

216 **Statistical analyses**

217 Our goal was to verify if species with certain traits were more
218 likely to contribute to dark diversity. Therefore, our response
219 variable was the proportion of times each species belonged to dark
220 diversity in relation to its species pool across vegetation types,
221 termed herein the ‘dark diversity index’ (DDi). The explanatory
222 variables were functional traits (or trait states) of species.

223 In a first step, we checked for correlations among functional traits.
224 Spearman’s rank correlations were conducted for continuous
225 variable comparisons, Mann-Whitney tests for continuous-
226 categorical variable comparisons, and Eta correlation coefficients
227 were generated for categorical variable comparisons. Values above

228 0.7 were considered indicative of collinearity (Dormann *et al.*,
229 2013).

230 Next, we assessed the univariate correlation between functional
231 traits and the probability of belonging to dark diversity; for
232 categorical/binary variables we used the Kruskal Wallis test,
233 whereas Spearman rank correlation was used for continuous and
234 ordinal variables.

235 Even if some traits were not revealed to be important in univariate
236 correlations, they might be important only when other factors are
237 also considered. To establish the unique contribution of each trait
238 to the probability of being part of dark diversity, we used a random
239 forest (RF) regression model (Breiman, 2001), implemented within
240 the randomForest R package (Liaw&Wiener, 2002). In this
241 analysis, the number of trees (ntree) was set to 5000, and the
242 number of predictors sampled for splitting at each node (mtry) was
243 set to 6, which represents the default value suggested for
244 regression RF models, i.e. number of predictor variables/3. Node
245 size (nodesize) was kept as default, i.e. 5 for regression. After
246 running the model, and in order to verify if species with certain
247 traits were more likely to contribute to dark diversity, we
248 quantified the importance of each predictive variable by
249 calculating the Mean Decrease Accuracy (%IncMSE). Merrill

250 (2009) demonstrated that this latter measure provides the highest
251 stability compared to node purity measures.

252

253 **Results**

254 **Species pool, observed species and dark diversity**

255 The number of **hoverfly** species representing observed and dark
256 diversity, as well as **diversity completeness**, varied between
257 different vegetation types (Fig. 3).

258

259 Figure 3. Number of species in dark diversity (blue), observed
260 diversity (dark green), in the species pool (pale green) and the
261 values of Diversity Completeness for each vegetation type (A-K,
262 see Fig. 2 legend).

263

264

265 The mean number of **hoverfly** species for species pools was 276.1
266 (+/-39.1 SD), for observed diversity it was 242.7 (+/-66.3 SD), and
267 for dark diversity it was 83.0 (+/-39.6 SD) across all vegetation
268 types. The most diverse species pool (355 species) was in Beech
269 and mixed beech forests (E), whereas Acidophilous oak and mixed
270 oak - hornbeam forests (D) exhibited the least diverse species pool
271 (227 species) (Fig. 3). In terms of numbers of observed species, the
272 richest vegetation type (402 species) was again Beech and mixed

273 beech forests (E), and the lowest number of observed hoverfly
274 species (136 species) was recorded from Southwest Balkan sub-
275 Mediterranean mixed oak forests (H). Hoverfly dark diversity was
276 lowest in Mediterranean mixed forests (J) (33 species or 11.9% of
277 species from the total number of species within this vegetation
278 type) and in Beech and mixed beech forests (E) (36 species,
279 10.1%), which had values of Diversity Completeness of 2.1 and
280 2.4, respectively. The highest values of dark diversity were in
281 Southwest Balkan sub-Mediterranean mixed oak forests (H) (162
282 species, 62.8%), reflected also in the lowest value of Diversity
283 Completeness (-0.2) and in Alpine, subalpine and oro-
284 Mediterranean vegetation (A) (140 species, 45%).

285

286 **Dark diversity and functional traits**

287

288 After excluding highly correlated variables, we retained 18 traits or
289 trait states for further analyses. Individual correlations between the
290 DDi and each functional trait are shown in Tab. 2.

291

292 Table 2. Correlations between the dark diversity index (DDi) and
293 functional traits.

294

295 The DDi was found to be significantly correlated and had strongest
296 correlation with four of the larval feeding modes (phytophagous on
297 bulbs, saproxylic, phytophagous on roots, and zoophagous), but
298 here does not appear to be a significant correlation between DDi
299 and the saprophagous larval feeding mode.

300 It also showed significant correlation with specific functional traits
301 states such as wide distribution, having no or short body pile, lack
302 or small inundation tolerance as well as long duration of larval
303 development. Additionally, the DDi was found to be significantly
304 correlated with body robustness, bad flight ability and shorter body
305 length.

306

307 Three larval feeding modes were the most significant variables
308 according to %IncMSE values (saproxylic = 54.2, phytophagous
309 on bulbs = 53.2, phytophagous on roots = 51.9) (Fig. 4), matching
310 the three most significant individual correlations with the DDi
311 (Tab. 2). Flight period, inundation tolerance, body shape and
312 human impact tolerance were also found to be very important
313 explanatory variables contributing to the probability of a species
314 being part of dark diversity, each of which presented a %IncMSE
315 value > 40.0. However, when assessed individually, human impact
316 tolerance and flight period were no longer important explanatory
317 variables.

318

319 Figure 4. Functional traits and trait states showing relative
320 importance (%IncMSE) for dark diversity of hoverflies in
321 Southeast Europe.

322

323 **Discussion**

324 Several studies in recent years have addressed the significance and
325 possible applications of investigating dark diversity (e.g. Pärtel *et*
326 *al.*, 2011; Pärtel, 2014; Ronk, 2016; Lewis *et al.*, 2017). However,
327 to the best of our knowledge, no previous study has addressed the
328 dark diversity of any insect group, which is perhaps unsurprising
329 given that invertebrates **have been** historically neglected in
330 conservation studies (Zamin *et al.*, 2010; Cardoso *et al.*, 2011).
331 Thus, our study represents the first extensive assessment of dark
332 diversity among hoverflies across SE Europe. Furthermore, it
333 reveals which functional traits of hoverflies can be linked to dark
334 diversity, potentially revealing why certain species are often
335 missing from habitat types in which they could potentially thrive.

336

337 **Levels of hoverfly dark diversity across vegetation types**

338 Southwest Balkan sub-Mediterranean mixed oak forests showed
339 the highest level of dark diversity and lowest level of observed
340 diversity, as well as smallest value of **diversity completeness**. This

341 outcome may be because oak forests are in decline generally all
342 across Europe (Thomas, 2008; Sohar *et al.*, 2014) and most of the
343 respective habitat patches are small and scattered, limiting their
344 carrying capacity and inhibiting the metapopulation dynamics
345 important for sustaining populations. Southwest Balkan sub-
346 Mediterranean mixed oak forests have been exposed to intense
347 anthropogenic pressure over the last 2000 years, subjected to
348 constant felling (Mansourian *et al.*, 2013). This pressure has
349 resulted in overt destruction, size reductions and fragmentation of
350 these forests, as well as promoting edge effects (Robinson *et al.*,
351 1995). Jovičić *et al.* (2017) investigated the effect of landscape
352 structure on the two largest hoverfly genera (*Merodon* Meigen,
353 1803 and *Cheilosia* Maigen, 1822) and suggested that habitat
354 connectivity influences the species composition of habitats. Beside
355 the loss of connectivity and habitat loss, edge effect is one of the
356 main sources of disturbance originated in fragmented habitats
357 (Córdova-Lepe *et al.*, 2018). It has been demonstrated that edge
358 effects impact physical characteristics of the environment, leading
359 to increased temperatures and reduced humidity (Murcia, 1995).
360 Environmental conditions, altered by habitat fragmentation, often
361 drive species range shifts, particularly when it comes to species
362 with a high degree of habitat specialization (Warren *et al.*, 2001;
363 Bonte *et al.* 2009).

364 Additional causes of oak forests declines are pathogenic infection
365 of oak species (Jung *et al.*, 2000) and extreme weather (drought or
366 frost) (Thomas, 2008). However, it is human impact that appears to
367 be playing a crucial role in maintaining deciduous oakwood
368 forests. For instance, occasional fires have been shown to promote
369 the occurrence of oak (Abrams, 1992), and it seems that the recent
370 decline in applying traditional management strategies (such as
371 burning) has negatively affected oakwood assemblages (Hedl *et*
372 *al.*, 2010).

373 A second vegetation type that presented high levels of dark
374 diversity was Alpine, subalpine and oro-Mediterranean. Multiple
375 studies have demonstrated the sensitivity of these habitats (Ruiz *et*
376 *al.*, 2009; Gillaredeli *et al.*, 2013). The main reasons for the
377 vulnerability of this vegetation type are increased human impact
378 through infrastructural development (Pintaldi *et al.*, 2017) and high
379 levels of grazing (Firm *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, patches of alpine
380 and subalpine habitats are usually small and fragmented. Thus,
381 multiple characteristics of the Alpine, subalpine and oro-
382 Mediterranean vegetation type could be responsible for the high
383 dark diversity of hoverflies we report for this vegetation type.

384 Mediterranean mixed forests showed the lowest level of dark
385 diversity. Although Mediterranean habitats have been reported as
386 seriously degraded due to intensive human actions (King, 1997;

387 Blondel, 2006), it would seem that they are resilient to existing
388 pressures, at least in terms of their capability of hosting a large
389 proportion of hoverfly species. Many reports (di Castri, 1981;
390 Thompson, 2005) have explained this phenomenon as resulting
391 from long-term adaptation of ecosystems to humans in this region,
392 even going so far as to apply the term “co-evolution”. Large
393 expanses of this vegetation type, which are highly connected,
394 enable the existence of many species, including those that require
395 large areas to maintain viable populations, resulting in only 33
396 species being identified as contributing to dark diversity. Beech
397 and mixed beech forests, the most complete vegetation type,
398 showed the second lowest level of dark diversity, and presented the
399 largest species pool. This outcome can be explained by the fact that
400 these forests are among the best preserved in SE Europe (Meyer *et*
401 *al.*, 2003), providing suitable microhabitats for both larvae and
402 adults of hoverflies. Additionally, this result may be partially
403 attributable to geographical proximity to degraded oak forests from
404 which hoverflies may have migrated to find more favorable
405 conditions.

406

407 **Functional traits contributing to dark diversity**

408 Three different larval feeding modes were identified as the most
409 significant traits contributing to dark diversity. The importance of

410 larval type and particularly their food preferences have been well
411 established for many other aspects of hoverfly biology and ecology
412 (Schweiger *et al.*, 2007; Haenke *et al.*, 2009), and our results
413 suggest that these factors dictate which species might survive in
414 habitats that are apparently adequate. Larval feeding mode
415 indirectly reflects the level of specialization of a species.
416 Saproxylic hoverfly larvae, as well as phytophagous species that
417 develop in bulbs and roots, are considered specialists (van Veen,
418 2004, Müller *et al.*, 2011). Generalist species are widely regarded
419 as being at an advantage compared to specialists in adapting to
420 changing environmental conditions (Biesmeijer *et al.*, 2006,
421 Barthel *et al.*, 2014). Generalist species are likely favored under
422 conditions of detrimental change and should constitute the majority
423 of observed diversity, whereas specialists may be absent from
424 impacted habitats and contribute towards dark diversity. Different
425 saproxylic hoverflies require different stages of wood decay for the
426 development and nutrition of their larvae (Speight, 1989), which is
427 particularly important in clear-cut forests without tree retention
428 where the microhabitats of these species are directly destroyed
429 (Larrieu *et al.*, 2012). Due to their high level of specialization,
430 saproxylic hoverflies have no alternative for their development.
431 However, changes in forest management (heterogeneity of trees in
432 terms of age and size structure) may increase saproxylic hoverfly

433 diversity (Remeer, 2005). Regarding phytophagous larvae (both
434 those developing in bulbs and in roots), their specialization is
435 reflected in the connection to a specific plant species. Thus,
436 geographical distributions of phytophagous species are limited by
437 the existence of suitable habitat for their host plants, which is
438 particularly important when species are monophagous (Müller *et*
439 *al.*, 2011).

440 With further regard to host dependency, the period during which
441 species fly was also revealed to be of high importance for dark
442 diversity in our RF analysis, but not when tested individually.
443 Flight period of hoverflies is directly linked to food resource
444 availability, with a temporal mismatch between hoverfly activity
445 and when host plants representing their primary food source flower
446 (Graham-Taylor *et al.*, 2009). Increasing temperatures caused by
447 climate change might lead to further phenological asynchrony
448 (Memmott *et al.*, 2007), which would have a serious negative
449 impact on specialist species. Exploitation of food resources is
450 dependent on other functional traits, thus, complex interactions
451 between flight period and other traits are likely to have a
452 synergistic effect on dark diversity.

453 Our results also indicate the significance of inundation tolerance
454 for the dark diversity of hoverflies; species with lower inundation
455 tolerance contribute more to hoverfly dark diversity. Inundation-

456 tolerant species can adapt to wet habitats and achieve higher
457 species richness under those environmental conditions (Keil *et al.*,
458 2008), reflected in their higher levels of observed diversity.
459 Additionally, inundation tolerance likely plays a crucial role in the
460 ability of species to survive challenging conditions. For example,
461 dark diversity of hoverflies is lowest in Mediterranean mixed
462 forests, even though flooding and extensive land degradation and
463 erosion often occur in that habitat (Poesen & Hooke, 1997).
464 Tolerance of human impacts determines the ability of a species to
465 persist in increasingly changing environments where agricultural
466 intensification, intensive grazing, forestry or urbanization are
467 taking place, ensuring resilient species have an advantage over
468 more sensitive ones (Winfrey *et al.*, 2011). Evolutionary processes
469 through which resilience develops not only result in species
470 surviving and reproducing in impacted habitats (Souza *et al.*,
471 2014), but also endow robustness against other types of
472 disturbances (Basley *et al.*, 2018). Accordingly, widely distributed
473 generalist species with the ability to thrive in different types of
474 habitats are those most likely to be resilient to human impacts
475 (Schweiger *et al.*, 2007).
476 Body shape is significant in shaping patterns of dark diversity
477 because it influences species' dispersal ability (Wootton, 2003;

478 García-Barros, 2015), with species contributing to dark diversity in
479 general having lower dispersal capacities (Riibak *et al.*, 2015).

480 Precisely, the results of our study indicate that robust body shape
481 appears to be very important for range expansion, representing one
482 of the trait states with higher probability of belonging to dark
483 diversity. Even though other measures directly related to dispersal
484 ability were not identified as being of eminent importance to dark
485 diversity in our study, body shape still provides useful insights into
486 the potential of a species to disperse. This functional trait
487 contributes to species being able to overcome challenging
488 environmental conditions (Hernández *et al.*, 2011), as well as to
489 extend their current range and invade new suitable areas.
490 Additionally, species with well-developed dispersal abilities are
491 less affected by habitat fragmentation, as they can migrate between
492 suitable habitat patches (Thomas, 2000). Apart from its link to
493 dispersal ability, robust body shape might also contribute a hitherto
494 unknown mechanism of physiological or behavioral adaptation
495 important for dark diversity for which we currently have no
496 evidence.

497

498 **Application of dark diversity concept in hoverfly conservation**

499 Investigation of dark diversity can contribute to prioritization of
500 conservation efforts of both species and their habitats. However, so

501 far, a small number of research studies has tackled this topic
502 (Yoshioka *et al.*, 2014; Ronk *et al.*, 2015, Lewis *et al.*, 2017,
503 Moeslund *et al.*, 2017). These studies highlight two main reasons
504 for studying dark diversity in the light of conservation. Firstly,
505 high levels of dark diversity in certain areas could imply the
506 existence of environmental disruptors. Secondly, apparently
507 suitable areas that exhibit a large portion of missing species have
508 great restorative potential. Thus, assessing dark diversity in these
509 regions could inform to what extent we can expect conservation
510 activities to be prosperous. Bearing this in mind, our results
511 indicate that hoverfly habitats within Southwest Balkan sub-
512 Mediterranean mixed oak forests and Alpine, subalpine and oro-
513 Mediterranean vegetation should be targeted for conservation.
514 Beside contribution to the conservation of habitats, dark diversity
515 studies enable more precise conservation prioritization in respect
516 of species-based approach. Namely, linking functional traits and
517 dark diversity may guide conservation efforts towards more
518 sensitive species. Our study shows that certain traits such as highly
519 specialized larval feeding modes, lack of inundation tolerance or
520 flight period promote dark diversity of hoverflies. Identifying
521 species possessing these traits could be an additional criterion
522 when deciding which species should receive conservation
523 attention.

524

525 **Conclusion**

526 Our study shows that hoverfly dark diversity to varying degrees
527 occurs in every vegetation type in SE Europe. We found larval
528 feeding mode to be the trait of greatest importance to determining
529 species **probability** to be a part of dark diversity, where those
530 modes **reflecting higher specialization were more likely**
531 **represented in dark diversity**. Establishing which functional traits
532 are responsible for dark diversity can help identify the processes
533 causing this absence of species in a given habitat. Additionally,
534 these results contribute to more precise conservation prioritization
535 of both hoverfly species and their habitats.

536

537 **Acknowledgments:**

538 We kindly thank Dr. David Wagner for useful comments that
539 significantly improved the quality of this paper and John O'Brien
540 for English proofreading. This work was funded by the Ministry of
541 Education, Science and Technological Development of the
542 Republic of Serbia, Grants No. OI173002 and III43002, the
543 Provincial Secretariat for Science and Technological Development
544 of the Republic of Serbia, Grant No. 0601-504/3 and H2020
545 Project ANTARES, Grant No. 664387.

546

547 **Authors' contribution:** AV, PC and MM participated in the
548 design of the study, MM, SP and PC wrote the paper; AV, MM, SP
549 and BI participated in data collecting; MM, SP and PC performed
550 the analyses, MM, SP and BI prepared the figures; all authors
551 contributed to manuscript with comments and revision.

552

553 **Conflict of interest disclosure:** We certify that we have no actual
554 or potential conflict of interest.

555

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For Review Only

938 **Table legends**

939 Table 1. Functional traits and trait states of hoverflies in SE

940 Europe.

941

942 Table 2. Correlations between the dark diversity index (DDi) and

943 functional traits; rs, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient; H,

944 Kruskal-Wallis statistic. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

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946 **Figure legends**

947 Figure 1. Schematic diagram illustrating species pool, observed
948 and dark diversity.

949

950 Figure 2. Vegetation types in Southeast Europe. A-Alpine,
951 subalpine and oro-Mediterranean vegetation, B-Montane spruce
952 and mixed spruce forests, C-Montane pine forests, D-Acidophilous
953 oak and mixed oak - hornbeam forests, E-Beech and mixed beech
954 forests, F-Thermophilous mixed bitter, pedunculate or sessile oak
955 forests, G-Southeast Balkan sub-Mediterranean mixed oak forests,
956 H-Southwest Balkan sub-Mediterranean mixed oak forests, I-
957 Pannonian lowland mixed oak forests and steppes, J-Mediterranean
958 mixed forests, K-Hardwood alluvial forests, wet lowland forests
959 and swamps.

960

961 Figure 3. Number of species in dark diversity (blue), observed
962 diversity (dark green), in the species pool (pale green) and the
963 values of Diversity Completeness for each vegetation type (A-K,
964 see Fig. 2 legend).

965

966 Figure 4. Relative importance of functional traits and trait states
967 (%IncMSE) in explaining the probability of hoverfly species
968 belonging to dark diversity in Southeast Europe.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram illustrating species pool, observed and dark diversity.

187x133mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 2. Vegetation types in Southeast Europe. A-Alpine, subalpine and oro-Mediterranean vegetation, B-Montane spruce and mixed spruce forests, C-Montane pine forests, D-Acidophilous oak and mixed oak - hornbeam forests, E-Beech and mixed beech forests, F-Thermophilous mixed bitter, pedunculate or sessile oak forests, G-Southeast Balkan sub-Mediterranean mixed oak forests, H-Southwest Balkan sub-Mediterranean mixed oak forests, I-Pannonian lowland mixed oak forests and steppes, J-Mediterranean mixed forests, K-Hardwood alluvial forests, wet lowland forests and swamps.

297x210mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 3. Number of species in dark diversity (blue), observed diversity (dark green), in the species pool (pale green) and the values of Diversity Completeness for each vegetation type (A-K, see Fig. 2 legend).

406x181mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 4. Relative importance of functional traits and trait states (%IncMSE) in explaining the probability of hoverfly species belonging to dark diversity in Southeast Europe.

199x199mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Table 1. Functional traits and trait states of hoverflies in Southeast Europe.

Functional traits	Functional trait states
Larval feeding mode (categorical variable)	Phytophagous (roots)
	Phytophagous (bulbs)
	Zoophagous
	Saprophagous
	Saproxylic
Duration of larval development (ordinal variable)	Less than 2 months
	2-6 months
	7-12 months
	More than a year
Number of generations (ordinal variable)	Less than one generation
	One generation
	Two generations
	More than two generations
Inundation tolerance (ordinal variable)	Intolerant
	Tolerant (short breathing tube)
	Tolerant (medium breathing tube)
	Tolerant (long breathing tube)
Body shape (ordinal variable)	Elongated
	Mildly elongated
	Robust
Distribution (ordinal variable)	Endemic and/or relict
	Widely distributed
Body pile (ordinal variable)	Without or with short pile
	Long pile
Height at which species fly (ordinal variable)	Arboreal
	Near the ground
Flight ability (ordinal variable)	Bad (flying clumsy and on a very short distances)
	Good (flying freely across the area)
	very good (migrant species)
Human impact tolerance (ordinal variable)	Low (natural or only slightly changed habitat)
	Medium (low grazing, ecological friendly forestry)
	High (overgrazing, forest cutting, replacement of initial forest, agriculture, villages)
	Very high (destruction of habitat, intense agriculture as monoculture without borders, cities)
Period of flight (ordinal variable)	Early spring (March)
	Spring (April and May)
	Early summer (June)
	Summer (July, August and September)
	Autumn (October and November)
Body length (continuous variable)	/
Wing length (continuous variable)	/

Ratio wing/body (continuous variable) /

Number of habitats (continuous variable) /

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Table 2. Correlations between the dark diversity index (DDi) and functional traits; r_s , Spearman's rank correlation coefficient; H, Kruskal-Wallis statistic. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Functional traits	DDi (%)
phytophagous-roots	H = 22.93***
phytophagous-bulbs	H = 57.51***
zoophagous	H = 18.24***
saprophagous	H = 1.63
saproxyllic	H = 45.57***
duration of larval development	$r_s = 0.11^{**}$
number of generations	$r_s = -0.07$
inundation tolerance	$r_s = 0.26^{***}$
body shape	$r_s = -0.18^{***}$
flight period	$r_s = 0.01$
distribution	$r_s = 0.19^{***}$
body pile	$r_s = 0.11^{**}$
flight height	$r_s = -0.009$
flight ability	$r_s = -0.08^*$
human impact tolerance	$r_s = -0.04$
body length	$r_s = -0.09^*$
ratio wing/body	$r_s = 0.04$
number of habitats	$r_s = 0.05$